

FIND YOUR EFFECTIVE VALORISATION STRATEGY WITH THE IP4OS TOOLBOX.

VALORISATION CONSULTANCY FORM

The **Valorisation Consultancy Form** serves as the initial information hub for the multi-professional team. Researchers register their consultancy requests via this form. IP4OS provides a **blueprint** that institutions can freely adapt, modify and make available on their websites or other channels. Teams and institutions also ensure researchers are aware of this registration option.

Access the [blueprint here](#).

INTRODUCTION

Welcome to the Valorisation Consultancy Form!

This form registers a request for an Intellectual Property management consultation for your project. The information you provide forms a basis for the multi-professional team, which includes experts in Intellectual Property management and Open Science practices, to support you.

With their expertise and knowledge of the [IP4OS Synergy Framework](#), the team helps identify the optimal Intellectual Property management strategy for your research, balancing exploitation of rights with Open Science practices to maximise value: innovation, business potential, and FAIR access to outputs.

For confidentiality reasons, the team can only support researchers from its own institution.

Some remarks on the consultation:

A consultation builds on the information provided in four steps:

Please complete this form to register for an intellectual property consultancy session and provide your team with initial information about your project and valorisation plans. The information is indica-

ive and non-binding and will be treated confidentially under the team's confidentiality agreement.

The multi-professional team will review your submission and contact you to schedule a consultation.

Please also review the additional guidance on handling Intellectual Property and Open Science.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND PRIVACY NOTICE

[Institutions implement and ensure their own declarations with a mandatory "Accept"-button.]

KNOWLEDGE CORNER

Effective management of research outputs and assets is key to **maximising research excellence, impact, valorisation, and visibility**. This requires the **systematic identification of intellectual assets** (research artefacts and results) and the **definition of clear valorisation and value-creation goals**, supported by appropriate **IP management aligned with Open Science practices**.

The level of openness and reusability should be determined case by case, guided by the nature of the assets, the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," applicable legal and institutional frameworks, and the objectives of the authors/rightsholders.

KNOWLEDGE CORNER ON INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY AND OPEN SCIENCE

Do you require further information on intellectual property rights, Open Science, and opportunities to generate value from your research outcomes? If yes, then check the box and have a look in the knowledge corner.

YES NO

“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”: a principle encouraging maximum sharing, but recognising that factors such as privacy may justify proportionate barriers.

Copyright: The exclusive legal right to reproduce, publish, and distribute a creative work. Librarians advise on managing and retaining these rights.

Embargo: A temporary restriction delaying open access to outputs.

FAIR Principles: FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable — making research outputs machine-actionable to foster sharing, redistribution, and reuse.

FAIR-R²L: FAIR-expansion to FAIR plus ‘Responsible Licensed’, adding the requirement to datasets being responsibly licensed and legally ready for reuse (whether in research or machine learning workflows or in use by AI).

Freedom to Operate (FTO): The analysis of whether a product or dataset can be used, shared, or commercialised without infringing third-party rights.

Intellectual assets: “[...] any result or product generated by any R&I activities” during (research artefacts) and at the end (research results) of a research process, such as Intellectual Property Right, data, know-how, and more. Not all assets are (potentially) eligible for Intellectual Property protection.

Examples of Intellectual Assets:

1) Publications (papers, reports etc.); 2) Lectures, talks, presentations, learning material; 3) Inventions (and utility models); 4) Data sets (raw/processed data); 5) (Industrial) Designs; 6) Software and Code; 7) Multimedia; 8) Protocols and (research) methods; 9) Technical reports; 10) Topographies of integrated circuits; 11) Geographical information; 12) others

Intellectual Property “means the result of intellectual activities that is eligible for legal protection (by Intellectual Property rights) and includes inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names, images, and designs.” IP4OS focuses on finding ways of managing **Intellectual Property Rights** that are compatible with Open Science and Knowledge Valorisation goals, including potential downstream commercialisation.

Knowledge Valorisation: the “[...] process of creating social, [environmental] and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and transforming data, know-how and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society” ([source](#)).

This transformation is determined by availability, re-utilisation and re-usability of intellectual assets. The application of Intellectual Property Rights and Open Science practices serves as a key instrument for research Knowledge Valorisation, defining the control and/or specification of utilisation of intellectual assets and safeguarding the author's/innovator's rights.

The **simple Knowledge Valorisation Rubric** (blueprint [here](#), description [here](#)) is an effective tool to assess a) focus of intellectual assets (producing new or re-using existing intellectual assets), b) the level or conditions of re-use, c) timing for/of reuse.

Licensing: The process of granting permission for others to use intellectual property under defined conditions, for example, software licences.

“Open [...]” does not necessarily mean ignoring IP Rights or allowing free commercial use. It means increasing FAIR access to research outputs to boost innovation capacity.

“Open Access” refers in particular to the release of research outputs such as articles or books in a way that they are accessible and reusable without a fee. There are different business models associated with open, in terms of who pays for publication costs and how.

Open licensing: an approach to licensing that aims to maximise possibilities for access and re-use. The most famous examples of these are Creative Commons licences.

Open Science is “an approach to research based on open cooperative work that emphasises the sharing of knowledge, results and tools as early and widely as possible” ([source](#)). It aims at (long-term) availability of intellectual assets for further knowledge circulation and gain, reusability, co-creation and enhancement of innovative power and dissemination through no-or-low barrier (according to “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”) access to scientific outputs, enabling reuse for discovery, validation, and cumulative knowledge building. Openness fosters quality assurance and replicability, and strengthens reliability, integrity, and trust in science.

Examples of Open Science practices:

1) Applying the **FAIR** principles to research outcomes; 2) **pre-registration** and **registered report**; 3) publishing in **Open Access** journals; 4) Depositing and sharing data, software, scripts, and algorithms in **open repositories**; 5) Using **open licences** (e.g. Creative Commons, Open Hardware Licence etc.); 6) Providing **data management plans (DMPs)**; 7) Using **open data**; 8) **Documenting code** to support reuse and reproducibility; 9) **Sharing experimental protocols, workflows, and methodologies**; 10) Posting **preprints** to share results prior to formal publication; 11) others

Regulatory exclusivity: A non-patent intellectual property tool granting temporary market protection based on regulatory data, relevant in pharmaceutical valorisation strategies.

Repository: A digital platform – typically non-commercial – used to store, manage, and provide access to research outputs.

Rights Retention: The practice of ensuring authors keep their rights, only offering specific possibilities to publishers when signing publishing agreements.

Secondary Publication Rights (SPR): A legal framework allowing authors to make a version of their (publicly funded) published articles openly accessible through institutional or non-profit repositories, typically upon or after journal publication, and sometimes under certain conditions.

 Find the **Valorisation Consultancy Form blueprint here**, modify it to your needs and implement it on your website.

VALORISATION CONSULTANCY FORM

1. General information

Welcome to the main and final step of this form. Please tell us more about your project, possible outcomes (intellectual assets) and your intentions regarding intellectual property rights or possible reuse options.

<p>Are you the owner of the research objects (intellectual assets)?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> YES, but joint owner <input type="checkbox"/> NO (We recommend to clarify the ownership and the regulations on intellectual property or exploitation rights within your organisation before disclosing confidential or Intellectual Property-sensitive data via this form). <input type="checkbox"/> I don't know.</p>
<p>Institutional Affiliation</p>	
<p>Department</p>	
<p>Name</p>	
<p>Email</p>	
<p>Project (progress): <input type="checkbox"/> I am planning my research. <input type="checkbox"/> I am starting my new research project. <input type="checkbox"/> I am in the midst of my ongoing research project.</p>	
<p>Brief description of your plans: Please provide a summary of your ideas.</p>	
<p>Key goals: Please list the primary objectives/outcomes/results of your research and describe your plans for valorisation (if applicable).</p>	
<p>Specific interests in the field of Intellectual Property and Open Science</p>	
<p>Has a Data Management Plan been developed yet?</p>	
<p>Does a partner agreement exist (if applicable)?</p>	
<p>Specify the (intended) funding scheme: If possible, provide information such as 'a third-party funded research project, publicly funded research project, private sector funding', etc. If applicable, what countries are involved in your consortium? Are there any funders' obligations regarding the valorisation strategy?</p>	
<p>Are you familiar with Open Science practices and their relationship to intellectual property?</p>	
<p>Have you participated in Open Science initiatives or projects?</p>	
<p>Are you familiar with the national law on employee inventions?</p>	

2. Defining the Intended Research Impact and Valorisation Pathways, Intellectual Assets, Intellectual Property Rights and Licenses

Effectively managing research outputs and assets is crucial for maximising the research’s excellence, impact, valorisation and visibility.

In the following tables you can provide initial information on your intentions for the use of your intellectual assets. Note that each intellectual asset has to be listed separately (start filling for a further intellectual asset after STEP 4.)

Provide as much information as possible; the team will help fill any gaps.

STEP 1 - What are your research goals, values and intended impact to be achieved?		-Free text-	
STEP 2 - Role focus: Identifying intellectual assets Identify and list all intellectual assets (research artefacts and results) expected from your project for which you seek consultation on usage rights.			
2.1 Producing new intellectual assets Determine if you are producing new outputs. <i>Guiding question: Which Intellectual Property tools ensure fit-for-purpose practice?</i>		2.2 Reusing existing intellectual assets Determine what existing outputs you aim to reuse. <i>Guiding question: Which licences apply, and under what conditions?</i>	
Name the intellectual asset you will produce <i>[Note: Name each asset separately. Start with the first asset, complete STEPs 3 and 4, then proceed to the next asset.]</i>	Select the intended Intellectual Property Right or Licence Note: For Trade Secrets & Know-How no reusability specification applicable	Name an existing intellectual asset you will reuse	Name the assigned Intellectual Property Right or Licence
-Freetext: new intellectual asset 1-	-Dropdown- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patent • Copyright • Trademark/Tradename • Plant Variety Right • Industrial Design 6 Aesthetic Innovation • Geographical Indication • Licence/Licence agreements • Creative Commons license (please specify in the consultation) • None of the above • Other (please specify in the consultation) 	-Freetext-	-Freetext-
STEP 3 - Level of reuse Determine the output’s openness. <i>Guiding question: Which licence or access mechanism fits best, and under what conditions?</i>		STEP 3 - Conditions of reuse Clarify reuse licences, exceptions or limitations and adhere to them. Follow the openness conditions of reused outputs to ensure compliance. <i>Guiding question: Which licences apply, and under what conditions?</i>	
-Dropdown- • Limited • Medium • High		-Freetext-	
STEP 4 - Timing Determine when to apply Intellectual Property Rights or Licences (before disclosure, before publication, or after FAIR sharing). <i>Guiding question: Which Intellectual Property tools at this stage best preserve future options and enable responsible sharing?</i>		STEP 4 - Timing Reuse according to the licence/ law/exception/other provision.	
Start date	For how long?	Start date	For how long?
-Freetext-	-Freetext-	-Freetext-	-Freetext-
-Enable more rows in the same structure (starting with “Name intellectual asset you will produce”) for further assets-			

Thank you for your interest and data provided.

A team-member will reach out to you soon regarding your consultation process.

For any other questions reach out to the consultation team: [Name, eMail]

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